

MORPHOLOGY AND INFILTRATION DYNAMICS OF LIQUID SILICONIZED CARBON/CARBON

Frank H. Gern, Walter Krenkel

German Aerospace Research Establishment (DLR)

Institute of Structures and Design

Pfaffenwaldring 38-40

70569 Stuttgart, Germany

ABSTRACT

This paper describes the investigation of morphology and infiltration dynamics of ceramic matrix composites (CMC) fabricated via liquid silicon infiltration (LSI) of porous carbon/carbon preforms. One of the main characteristics of this preform is its open porosity influencing the dosage of infiltrated silicon. Numerical simulation as well as experimental measurement of phase shares of a manufactured C/C-SiC plate have been conducted. Calculated values are in good accordance with experimental results. Additionally, oxidation resistance of the material was investigated.

Keywords: Ceramic matrix composites, C/C-SiC, liquid silicon infiltration, LSI process, morphology, phase composition

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites show superior properties and high specific strength values under extreme thermal and environmental conditions. The fabrication of structural components for applications in aerospace or energy systems necessitates the development of short and cost-effective manufacturing cycles. One promising route satisfying these requirements is the infiltration of liquid silicon into porous carbon/carbon preforms. This LSI process is characterized by manufacturing times of two weeks and consists of three distinct process steps [1, 2]:

- CFRP manufacturing of the component,
- pyrolysis of the polymeric precursor and formation of a porous C/C preform,
- infiltration of liquid silicon and formation of the C/C-SiC composite.

Several structural components like heat shields for re-entry capsules [3] and intake ramps for hypersonic engines [4] have been realized and have demonstrated the feasibility of this manufacturing route for complex lightweight structures.

2. C/C-MICROSTRUCTURE

C/C-SiC fabrication is based upon the manufacture of a suitable CFRP preform by common techniques like resin transfer moulding (RTM) or autoclave technology. Using the polymeric precursor XP-60 (with a carbon yield of 64% after pyrolysis up to 900°C) and high tenacity carbon fabrics (e.g. Akzo's HTA) CFRP components with fibre volume contents of about 50% have been realized. For these investigations, a plate of 300 × 300mm² and a thickness of 3mm was manufactured using 14 plain weave fabric layers in 0°/90° orientation.

During subsequent pyrolysis the precursor's shrinkage leads to the formation of a characteristic microcrack pattern with translamellar capillary channels facilitating infiltration of liquid silicon into the porous carbon/carbon preform [5]. In order to obtain appropriate silicon dosage reliable determination of the open porosity of the carbon/carbon is necessary. In general, experimental measurement of porosity is mainly conducted using three methods:

- mercury porosimetry,
- helium pycnometry,
- water infiltration.

Water infiltration and pycnometry are suitable to determine bulk porosity of the specimen, whereas mercury porosimetry is widely in use to measure statistical pore size distributions [6]. Due to the high pressures used in mercury porosimetry this method seems not to be applicable for carbon/carbon preforms because of their rather fair mechanical properties. Pycnometry allows the examination of pore volumes with high precision but is only limited to small samples and measured values seem to be not transferable directly to silicon infiltration conditions.

For this reason, determination of porosity has been carried out using the water infiltration method. The procedure of water infiltration is standardized for porous ceramic materials and clearly defined in German standards (DIN 51056) [7]. Samples of the material are infiltrated with demineralized water under vacuum to ensure complete penetration. In principle, there is no limitation of sample size and therefore investigation of complete components could be possible. Bulk density ρ_R as well as bulk porosity e' are then determined by comparing the weights of the dry specimen m_1 , the under water weight m_2 and the weight of the infiltrated specimen m_3 :

$$\text{Density : } \rho_R = \frac{m_1}{m_3 - m_2} \cdot \rho_{\text{water}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Porosity : } e' = \frac{m_3 - m_1}{m_3 - m_2} \cdot \rho_{\text{water}} \quad (2)$$

Using this method, porosity of the manufactured carbon/carbon plate was determined to $e' = 18.9\%$ resulting in a density of $\rho_R = 1.38\text{g/cm}^3$. Investigation of SEM micrographs showed that open porosity is mainly formed by capillary channels with diameters ranging between 10 μm and 50 μm .

3. THEORETICAL ASPECTS

The formation of discrete translamellar capillary channels during pyrolysis ensures good penetration of the porous carbon/carbon preform and therefore high infiltration velocities. Figure 1 illustrates time dependence of infiltration velocity for capillary diameters d_K from

$10\mu\text{m}$ to $50\mu\text{m}$. With values between 2.5cm/s and 0.5cm/s the plate should be completely infiltrated within several minutes. Until now, infiltration lengths of up to 400mm have been realized in rectangular plates without important gradients in silicon concentration.

Figure 1: Infiltration velocity for capillary diameters from $10\mu\text{m}$ to $50\mu\text{m}$

The first contact of liquid silicon leads to the immediate formation of silicon carbide layers at the capillary walls, but due to the high infiltration velocities capillary diameters may be considered constant for short infiltration times. After initial silicon carbide formation the chemical reaction has to be maintained by diffusion of silicon atoms through the SiC layers into the reaction zone which is situated in the boundary region between carbon and silicon carbide [8]. Figure 2 shows schematically the formation of silicon carbide within one capillary channel filled with liquid silicon during the siliconizing process at temperatures above 1420°C .

Figure 2: Formation of silicon carbide at the capillary walls

Time dependence of capillary diameters has to be described using the thickness of the SiC layer d_{SiC} :

$$d_{K(t)} = d_{K0} - \delta d_{K(t)} = d_{K0} - 2 d_{SiC} \left(1 - \frac{1}{K_{MV}} \right) \quad (3)$$

In equation (3) K_{MV} is the molar volume coefficient given by the volume fraction of formed silicon carbide and converted matrix carbon. The thickness of the SiC layer itself may be expressed in terms of the binary diffusion coefficient D_e of the silicon atoms:

$$d_{SiC} = \sqrt{2 D_e \frac{M_C}{M_{Si}} \frac{\rho_{Si}}{\rho_C} \cdot t} \quad (4)$$

In equation (4) M_C and M_{Si} are the molar masses of carbon and silicon, ρ_C and ρ_{Si} the corresponding densities. Macroscopic silicon carbide formation in an entire component is determined by interaction of the total amount of all capillaries forming the open porosity of the part. Evidently, the time span required for complete silicon conversion is much longer in larger capillary segments than in smaller ones. For this reason, the share of residual free silicon in the component is dependent on the statistical distribution function of capillary diameters [9]. Time dependence of the macroscopic degree of silicon conversion therefore has to be expressed in terms of the statistical frequency p_i of the capillary diameters d_{K_i} :

$$\frac{V_{Si \text{ converted}}(t)}{V_{Si \text{ infiltrated}}} = 1 - \frac{\sum_i p_i \cdot d_{K_i(t)}}{\sum_i p_i \cdot d_{K0i}} = 1 - \frac{\sum_i p_i \cdot d_{K_i(t)}}{D_m} \quad (5)$$

D_m is the average capillary diameter of the component and is calculated by summation of all capillary diameters according to their statistical frequency.

Figure 3: Microstructure of the investigated C/C-SiC plate (I209/1)

Figure 3 shows the microstructure of the investigated C/C-SiC plate. The mass shares of carbon, silicon carbide and residual free silicon in the C/C-SiC part were calculated using equation (5). After two hours of silicon conversion at 1550°C the theoretical share of free silicon is 5.11%. 29.45% of the material should consist of silicon carbide and 65.44% of carbon, comprising the embedded fibres as well as residual carbon matrix.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The carbon/carbon plate was siliconized in a standard LSI process for 2 hours at 1550°C under vacuum to evaluate the theoretical approach. Samples were cut off and chemically etched in order to investigate the mass shares of the three material phases: carbon, silicon carbide and free silicon. Additionally, C/C-SiC samples were treated in oxidative atmosphere at temperatures of up to 1200°C to examine the oxidation stability in terms of mass and strength loss.

4.1. PHASE COMPOSITION

In case of a non-stoichiometrical reaction between silicon and the carbon matrix the LSI process leads to a residual amount of free silicon which is present as an intergranular phase between the SiC grains [10]. As X-ray images of the total plate only allow a qualitative examination of the silicon and silicon carbide distribution, the plate was cut into small samples of $25 \times 10 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ to investigate the phase composition by removing the silicon chemically and by quantifying its mass share.

Elementary silicon shows a very fair reactivity and is only soluble in alkali solutions like KOH and in mixtures of the acids HF and HNO₃. The latter method was used in a ratio of 10 parts hydrofluoric acid and one part nitric acid. During this etching, silicon first oxidises to silicon dioxide and subsequently reacts to a stable hexafluorocomplex according to the following equations:

The acids only affect free silicon whereas carbon and silicon carbide remain stable during etching. To determine the amount of these phases, one of them has additionally to be removed. The phase composition of the C/C-SiC materials can then be calculated after weighing the residual mass.

Due to the high fibre mass content of the plate (58.4%) the share of carbon is the greatest within the material. To remove the carbon completely the samples were exposed to air at 600°C for 140 hours. The mean mass loss after this treatment amounts to 60.1%. Assuming that in the ideal case no fibre reaction with silicon occurred, this value indicates that only a very small part of the carbon matrix is still present in the C/C-SiC material whereas most of it reacted to silicon carbide.

After this thermal treatment the samples were chemically etched for 17 hours in a HF/HNO₃ solution at 20°C. Due to the high accessibility of the SiC zones the acid reached all regions of residual free silicon and removed it completely. Figure 4 shows the ex-C/C-SiC microstructure after thermal and chemical treatment.

The chemical reaction of silicon leads to an additional mass loss of 15%, referring to the oxidised samples. This corresponds with a residual silicon content of 6% within the original C/C-SiC material. Summarizing the results for all samples, the mean phase composition of the C/C-SiC plate can be determined. Table 1 indicates that the measured values are in good accordance with the theoretical calculations.

Figure 4: Microstructure of the C/C-SiC plate after thermal oxidation at 600°C and chemical etching with HF/HNO₃ (10:1) at 20°C

C-fibres	C-matrix	silicon carbide	free silicon
58.4%	1.7%	33.9%	6.0%

Table 1: Experimental mass shares of the investigated C/C-SiC plate (I209/1)

4.2. OXIDATION RESISTANCE

Oxidation resistance of the silicon infiltrated carbon/carbon has been determined by exposure in oxidative atmosphere. In this case, oxidative mass loss is regarded to be indicative for the stability of the samples. For the experiments a high temperature furnace Linn High Therm HT 1600 Vac was used. Oxidation experiments comprising different temperatures (600°C, 900°C and 1200°C) at three furnace holding times (0.5h, 1h, 3h) were carried out. In order to ensure reproducible results the furnace atmosphere was changed to nitrogen during heating and cooling phases. Based on preliminary experiments the dimensions of the oxidation samples were defined to 80 × 10 × 3mm³.

In the C/C-SiC material, oxidation mainly takes place at the free edges where the carbon fibres are directly in contact with oxygen. For this reason, oxidation behaviour is of orthotropic character and mass loss is mainly observed within the direction of the carbon fibre bundles. Due to this free edge problem, external sealing of the samples was conducted in order to improve oxidation resistance.

C/C-SiC materials show good compatibility with external oxidation protection coatings like chemical vapour deposited silicon carbide. The adhesion of this CVD-SiC coating on the C/C-SiC substrate is very high as it is for carbon/carbon. Nevertheless, due to a mismatch of

thermal expansion coefficients the coating shows microcracks allowing diffusion of oxygen into the substrate material at temperatures below 900°C. For elevated temperatures of 1200°C these microcracks are closed resulting in an even higher oxidation resistance.

Further improvement of thermal stability is possible applying an additional external glass coating (SiO₂) in order to seal microcracks in the CVD-SiC. Figure 5 illustrates oxidation behaviour of coated and uncoated C/C-SiC substrates in comparison to commercially available carbon/carbon after exposure in air at 900°C and 1200°C, respectively.

Figure 5: Mass loss of C/C-SiC materials in comparison to carbon/carbon after thermal treatment in air for 3 hours

5. CONCLUSIONS

Ceramic matrix composites have been fabricated via the liquid silicon infiltration of porous carbon/carbon. Numerical simulation of the material's phase composition is based on a microstructural approach to macroscopic silicon conversion. Calculated values of phase shares were evaluated by experimental measurements based on thermal and chemical treatment. For this purpose, residual free silicon was removed by etching with a mixture of hydrofluoric acid and nitric acid. The carbon was eliminated by oxidation. Calculated values and measured phase shares are in good accordance showing a material composition of two thirds in mass of carbon and one third in mass of silicon carbide. Further process development has to be focused on the reduction of residual free silicon which is required for high temperature applications.

In addition, oxidation behaviour of the material was investigated. Due to an internal silicon carbide protection oxidation resistance of the C/C-SiC composite is considerably higher than for commercial carbon/carbon. Real components of high complexity have already been manufactured via the LSI route and have demonstrated the applicability of this process.

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